

MARKET DYNAMICS AND CHALLENGES IN HYBRID MAIZE SEED SELLING: A STUDY OF TRIBAL FARMERS AND DEALERS OF SABARKANTHA DISTRICT

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Abstract

The present study analyzed the market share, buying behaviour of hybrid maize-growing tribal farmers, dealers' outlook, and constraints in seed sales in Sabarkantha district of Gujarat state. Multistage sampling technique was employed to select 120 farmers and 15 dealers for the study. Tabular method, percentages, and Garrett's ranking method were utilized for analysis. Among the seeds, maize was found to be available in all the dealer's shops (100%), followed by green gram seeds (80%). Kaveri Seeds led in market share (73.33%), followed by Advanta (66.67%) and Rasi (60.00%). Kaveri Seeds also had the highest shop presence (80%), followed by Advanta (73.33%) and Rasi Seeds (66.67%). Farmers preferred Kaveri seeds (21.67%), followed by Advanta (15.00%) and Rasi seeds (14.17%). Majority of farmers (65.83%) purchased seeds at sowing time, mainly from retailers (76.66%), with 69.17% paying in cash. Satisfaction with seed quality was high (88.33%) among farmers. Among dealers, 40% had 10-15 years of experience, indicating market expertise. Quality was crucial to 93.33% dealers, highlighting its impact on sales. Shriram Seeds provided the highest dealer margin (24.26%). Most dealers (80%) prioritized increasing margins, focusing on profitability. Major challenges included competition and insufficient field staff, affecting effective promotion. Creating market reach for the hybrid maize tribal farmers is in high need and the same needs government bodies intervention to develop markets in major maize growing districts of the state.

Keywords: Hybrid Maize, Market share, Constraints, Dealers, Tribal Areas.

Introduction

Maize (*Zea mays* L.) is one of the most versatile emerging crops having wider adaptability under different agro-climatic conditions. Maize is known as the "queen of cereals" because it has the highest genetic yield potential among the cereals. It directly adds approximately 10 per cent to the Indian food basket and 5 per cent to the global supply of dietary energy. At global levels, USA reports the highest production of 382.89 million tonnes, followed by China with 272.55 million tonnes in 2023-24. In India, maize is the third most important food crop after rice and wheat. It is grown mainly during kharif season which covers 80 per cent of total area. In North Gujarat, Arvalli post the highest production at 1188.18 thousand tonnes. Sabarkantha had a production of 432.23 thousand tonnes. As the present study deals with market dynamics of maize in tribal areas in Gujarat, Sabarkantha with ST population of 542,156 was selected as it is a maize growing area as well. The present study was undertaken to study the market share, buying behavior, dealers outlook of different hybrid maize seed companies and constraints faced by dealers in selling of hybrid maize seeds.

Material and Methods

The multistage sampling approach was used to achieve the study's objectives. At the first stage, Sabarkantha district was selected purposively because Sabarkantha was the second highest maize producing district in North Gujarat. In the second stage on the basis of highest population of tribal and highest sowing area of kharif maize three talukas viz. Khedbrahmaa, Vijaynagar and Poshina were selected purposively. In the third stage, from each talukas 5 villages were selected randomly and from each village 8 farmers were selected and 5 dealers from each taluka were selected randomly. Thus, a total of 120 farmers and 15 dealers were selected from the Sabarkantha. Percentage analysis was employed to examine the market share, buying behavior

and dealer's outlook, while the constraints were examined using the Garrett ranking method. The formulation of analytical tools used in the study is as follows:

Percentage analysis = (Value/Total value) × 100%

$$= \frac{X}{Y} \times 100$$

Where,

X = No. of respondents

Y = Total no. of respondents

Coming to Garrett's ranking, the respondents were asked to assign ranks for all factors and the outcome of such ranking was converted into score value with the help of the following formula:

$$\text{Percent position} = \frac{100(R_{ij} - 0.5)}{N_j}$$

Where,

R_{ij} = Rank given for the i^{th} variable by j^{th} respondents

N_j = Number of variables ranked by j^{th} respondents

Results and Discussion

Market share of hybrid maize seeds companies

Table 1 exhibits the major companies preferred by hybrid maize-growing tribal farmers. The results showed that the highest volume of seeds purchased for hybrid maize crops was accounted for by Kaveri Seeds Pvt. Ltd. (21.67%) followed by Advanta Seeds Pvt. Ltd. (15.00%), Rasi Seeds Pvt. Ltd. (14.17%), Pioneer Seeds Pvt. Ltd. (13.33%), Navbharat Seeds Pvt. Ltd. (10.00%), Srikar Seeds Pvt. Ltd. (6.67%), Remik Agri Seeds Pvt. Ltd. (07.50%), Sagarlaxmi Seeds Pvt. Ltd. (05.83%), Shriram Seeds Pvt. Ltd. (03.33%) and Arose Seeds Pvt. Ltd. (02.50%).

Table 1. Distribution of hybrid maize growing tribal farmer according to various hybrid maize seed companies (n=120)

Sr. No.	Company name	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
1.	Kaveri Seeds Pvt. Ltd.	26	21.67
2.	Advanta Seeds Pvt. Ltd.	18	15.00
3.	Rasi Seeds Pvt. Ltd.	17	14.17
4.	Navbharat Seeds Pvt. Ltd.	12	10.00
5.	Remik Agri Seeds Pvt. Ltd.	09	07.50
6.	Sagarlaxmi Seeds Pvt. Ltd.	07	05.83
7.	Srikar Seeds Pvt. Ltd.	08	06.67
8.	Pioneer Seed Pvt. Ltd.	16	13.33

9.	Arose Seeds Pvt. Ltd.	03	02.50
10.	Shriram Seeds Pvt. Ltd.	04	03.33
Total:		120	100.00

Buying behavior of hybrid maize growing tribal farmers According to time of purchase of hybrid maize seeds

Below table 2 displayed that 65.83 per cent farmers purchased seeds at the time of sowing, whereas 34.17 per cent farmer purchased seeds before the time of sowing (Rajgor *et al.*, 2017).

Table 2: Time of purchase of hybrid maize seeds by farmers

(n=120)

Sr. No.	Purchasing time	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
1.	At the time of sowing	79	65.83
2.	Before the time of sowing	41	34.17
Total:		120	100.00

According to source of purchase of hybrid maize seeds

Table 3 indicated that 77.50 per cent of farmers had purchased hybrid maize seeds from retailers followed by 15.83 per cent farmers had purchased seed from co-operative society also that, 06.67 per cent from

wholesalers. The highest proportion of hybrid maize seeds were purchased from retailers likely due to the easy availability of seeds nearby and possibly credit offered by retailers.

Table 3: Distribution of hybrid maize growing tribal farmers as per source of purchase

(n=120)

Sr. No.	Source	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
1.	Wholesaler	08	06.67
2.	Retailer	93	77.50
3.	Co-operative society	19	15.83
Total:		120	100.00

According to satisfaction level

Table 4 showed that 88.33 per cent of hybrid maize growers were satisfied with the previous year's seeds, while 11.67 per cent of hybrid maize growers were unsatisfied with respect to the hybrid maize seeds.

Table 4: Satisfaction of farmers regarding hybrid maize variety grown in previous season

(n=120)

Sr. No.	Satisfaction level	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
1.	Satisfied	106	88.33
2.	Unsatisfied	14	11.67
Total:		120	100.00

According to mode of payment

Table 5 revealed that 69.17 per cent purchased hybrid maize seeds with cash followed by 20.83 per cent purchased on credit and cash both, 10.00 per cent hybrid maize farmers purchased on credit. This pattern of payment mode showed that the majority of hybrid maize growing tribal farmers purchased seeds with cash.

Table 5: Mode of payment to purchase of hybrid maize seeds

(n=120)

Sr. No.	Mode of payment	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
1.	Cash	83	69.17
2.	Credit	12	10.00
3.	Cash and credit	25	20.83
Total:		120	100.00

Dealer's outlook of different hybrid maize seed companies

Business experience of hybrid maize seed dealers

Table 6 showed that the largest percentage (40.00%) of hybrid maize seed dealers had between 11 to 15 years of experience. This was

followed by (26.67%) of dealers with 06 to 10 years of experience, more than 15 years' business experience 20.00 per cent and 13.33 per cent up to 05 years business experience of dealers (Dubey *et al.* 2023).

Table 6: Distribution of hybrid maize dealers according to their business experience

(n=15)

Sr. No.	Business experience	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
1.	Up to 5 years	02	13.33
2.	6 to 10 years	04	26.67
3.	11 to 15 years	06	40.00
4.	More than 15 years	03	20.00
Total:		15	100.00

Classification of major crops seeds as per availability in dealers shop

Table 7 showed that maize seed had the highest availability (100.00%) in dealer's shops, followed by green gram seed availability (80.00%), bajra seed (60.00%) and cotton seed (53.33%). castor and mustard seeds had availability rates of 33.33 per cent and 46.67 per cent respectively. The lowest availability of seed crops was found for groundnut seed (40.00%).

Table 7: Classification of major crops seed available in dealers' shop

(n=15)			
Sr. No.	Crop seed	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
1.	Maize	15	100.00
2.	Cotton	08	53.33
3.	Castor	05	33.33
4.	Green gram	12	80.00
5.	Bajra	09	60.00
6.	Mustard	07	46.67
7.	Ground nut	06	40.00

Different companies' hybrid maize seed availability in dealers shop

Kaveri Seeds Pvt. Ltd. had the highest presence with 80.00 per cent representation, followed closely by Advanta Seeds Pvt. Ltd. at 73.33 per cent and Rasi Seeds Pvt. Ltd. At (66.67%) Pioneer seeds Pvt. Ltd. and Navbharat Seeds Pvt. Ltd. were also notable with 60.00 per cent

and 53.33 per cent respectively. Srikar Seeds Pvt. Ltd. accounted for 46.67 per cent of the dealer's stock, while Sagarlaxmi Seeds Pvt. Ltd. and Remik Agri Seeds Pvt. Ltd. had 33.33 per cent and 26.67 per cent representation, respectively. Shriram Seeds Pvt. Ltd. and Arose Seeds Pvt. Ltd. rounded out the list with 20.00 per cent and 13.33 per cent respectively.

Table 8: Distribution of dealers according to different companies' hybrid maize seeds availability in shop

(n=15)			
Sr. No.	Name of Company	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
1.	Kaveri Seeds Pvt. Ltd.	12	80.00
2.	Advanta Seeds Pvt. Ltd.	11	73.33
3.	Rasi Seeds Pvt. Ltd.	10	66.67
4.	Navbharat Seeds Pvt. Ltd.	08	53.33
5.	Remik Agri Seeds Pvt. Ltd.	04	26.67
6.	Sagarlaxmi Seeds Pvt. Ltd.	05	33.33
7.	Srikar Seeds Pvt. Ltd.	07	46.67
8.	Pioneer Seed Pvt. Ltd.	09	60.00
9.	Arose Seeds Pvt. Ltd.	02	13.33
10.	Shriram Seeds Pvt. Ltd.	03	20.00

Dealer association with various hybrid maize seed companies over the year

Table 9 revealed that Kaveri Seeds Pvt. Ltd. 26.67 per cent of dealers had 10-15 years of experience, followed by 20.00 per cent with 2-5 years and 5 -10 years, 06.67 per cent with less than 2 years and more

than 15 year of association. Advanta Seeds Pvt. Ltd. had the highest percentage (26.67%) of dealers with 2-5 years of experience, followed by 20 per cent with less than 2 years and 5-10 years and 06.67 per cent 10-15 years

Table 9-Dealer association with various hybrid maize seed companies over the year

(n=15)						
Sr. No.	Company Name	Frequency				
		<2 year	2-5 years	5-10 years	10-15 years	>15 years
1.	Kaveri Seeds	1 (6.67)	3 (20.00)	3 (20.00)	4 (26.67)	1 (6.67)
2.	Advanta Seeds	3 (20.00)	4 (26.67)	3 (20.00)	1 (6.67)	0 (0.00)
3.	Rasi Seeds	2 (13.33)	4 (26.67)	4 (26.67)	1 (6.67)	0 (0.00)
4.	Navbharat Seeds	2 (13.33)	3 (20.00)	3 (20.00)	1 (6.67)	0 (0.00)
5.	Remik Agri Seeds	2 (13.33)	3 (20.00)	0 (0.00)	0 (0.00)	0 (0.00)
6.	Sagarlaxmi Seeds	1 (6.67)	3 (20.00)	2 (13.33)	0 (0.00)	0 (0.00)
7.	Srikar Seeds	5 (33.33)	2 (13.33)	0 (0.00)	0 (0.00)	0 (0.00)
8.	Pioneer Seeds	2 (13.33)	2 (13.33)	4 (26.67)	1 (6.67)	1 (6.67)
9.	Arose Seeds	2 (13.33)	1 (6.67)	0 (0.00)	0 (0.00)	0 (0.00)
10.	Shriram Seeds	0 (0.00)	2 (13.33)	2 (13.33)	2 (13.33)	0 (0.00)

Note: Figures in parentheses indicated the percentage to dealer association with companies

Purchase of different companies' hybrid maize seeds preference given by dealers

Table 10 showed that price was a significant consideration for 60.00 per cent of dealers. Competitive pricing affected the cost to farmers and significantly influenced their purchasing choices. Nearly half of the dealers 46.67 per cent considered the promotional schemes offered

by seed companies as effective promotions could boost sales and attract more customers. Time availability was a concern for 40.00 per cent of dealers. Ensuring that seeds were available when needed was crucial for planting schedules and overall agricultural planning. Lastly, credit policy was important to 33.33 per cent of dealers.

Table 10: Distribution of dealer according to preference while purchasing maize seeds from (n=15)

Sr. No.	Preference	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
1.	Quality	14	93.33
2.	Price	09	60.00
3.	Demand by farmer	10	66.67
4.	Credit policy	05	33.33
5.	Promotional scheme	07	46.67
6.	Time availability	06	40.00
7.	Brand image	12	80.00

Different brand wise dealer's margin in hybrid maize seeds marketing

Table 11 revealed that dealers were getting the highest margin of 24.26 per cent on Shriram Seeds Pvt. Ltd.'s SMH-1172. This was followed by a 20.90 per cent margin on Arose Seeds Pvt. Ltd.'s Arose 5050, 20.13 per cent on Remik Agri Seeds Pvt. Ltd.'s HMR-7070 and 19.59 per cent on Srikar Seeds Pvt. Ltd.'s SS-Vasanti. Sagarlaxmi Seeds Pvt.

Ltd.'s Bhole offered a 17.45 per cent margin, while Navbharat Seeds Pvt. Ltd.'s NB111 provided a 17.29 per cent margin. Kaveri Seeds Pvt. Ltd.'s super 2020 had a margin of 15.94 per cent, followed by Advanta Seeds Pvt. Ltd.'s ADV 9293 at 15.22 per cent and Pioneer Seed Pvt. Ltd.'s P3502 at 14.71 per cent. The lowest margin was 12.62 per cent for Rasi Seeds Pvt. Ltd.'s HM-3499.

Table 11-Dealer's margin across the different brands of hybrid maize seeds

(n=15)

Sr. No.	Companies name	Product (variety)	Margin (%)
1.	Kaveri Seeds Pvt. Ltd.	Super 2020	15.94
2.	Advanta Seeds Pvt. Ltd.	ADV 9293	15.22
3.	Rasi Seeds Pvt. Ltd.	HM-3499	12.62
4.	Navbharat Seeds Pvt. Ltd.	NB 111	17.29
5.	Remik Agri Seeds Pvt. Ltd.	HMR-7070	20.13
6.	Sagarlaxmi Seeds Pvt. Ltd.	Bhole	17.45
7.	Srikar Seeds Pvt. Ltd.	SS-Vasanti	19.59
8.	Pioneer Seed Pvt. Ltd.	P3502	14.71
9.	Arose Seeds Pvt. Ltd.	Arose 5050	20.90
10.	Shriram Seeds Pvt. Ltd.	SMH-1172	24.26

Expectations of dealers from company

Table 12 revealed that 80.00 per cent of dealers had placed a high priority on increasing margins, indicating their desire for higher profitability from the companies. Following closely 66.67 per cent emphasized the crucial need for hybrid maize seeds to be easily and

timely available during the planting season, highlighting the logistical importance of seed availability. 60.00 per cent had high yield variety due to farmer constraint. 53.33 per cent had valued bonuses such as incentives and rewards offered by the companies, illustrating their appreciation for additional benefits beyond the product itself.

Table 12-Expectations of dealers from seed companies

(n=15)

Sr. No.	Expectations	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
1.	Increasing margin	12	80.00
2.	High yield variety	09	60.00
3.	Easily and timely availability of seed	10	66.67
4.	Bonus	08	53.33

Constraints faced by dealers in the selling of hybrid maize seeds

Table 13 displayed that hybrid maize seed dealers also faced several significant constraints that impacted their ability to effectively sell seeds. Among the most pressing issues was intense competition among dealers. This competitive environment made it challenging for

individual dealers to maintain market share and profitability. Followed by lack of field staff, lack of promotional scheme, credit sales and unavailability of seed at time of sowing (Kumar *et al.* 2014).

Table 13: Constraints faced by hybrid maize seed dealers during selling of hybrid maize

(n=15)

Sr. No.	Constraints	Garrett's Score	Rank
1.	Competition among dealer	55.53	I
2.	Lack of field staff	52.93	II
3.	Lack of promotional scheme	52.60	III

4.	Credit sales	47.20	IV
5.	Unavailability of seed at time of sowing	40.73	V

Conclusion

Maize seeds were available in all the dealer's shops in the tribal areas taken up in the study. Kaveri Seeds Pvt. Ltd. had the highest available in dealer's shop with 80.00 per cent representation. Most (21.67%) hybrid maize-growing tribal farmers preferred Kaveri seeds company's hybrid maize seed. Around 65.83 per cent hybrid maize growing tribal farmers purchased hybrid maize seed at the time of sowing. The majority (76.66%) hybrid maize growing tribal farmer purchased seeds from retailer's shops and on cash payment (69.17%). It was observed that 88.33 per cent hybrid maize growing tribal farmers were satisfied from previous year seeds. The majority (40.00%) of hybrid maize seed dealers had between greater than 10 to 15 years of experience. Majority dealer's association with various hybrid maize seed companies in the 2-5 years' category across multiple companies. Quality was the most critical factor with 93.33 per cent of dealers emphasizing its importance. Dealers were getting the highest margin of 24.26 per cent on Shriram Seeds Pvt. Ltd.'s SMH-1172. Majority of 80.00 per cent expectations of dealers had placed a high priority on increasing margins. Dealers faced major constraints of competition among dealers. Creating market reach for the hybrid maize tribal farmers is in high need. As maize being a highly traded commodity, the state governments should encourage developing modern markets at the district level in the major maize-growing belts to help the farmer access at the latest market information and support them to fetch maximum prices for their produce.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that they do not have any conflict of interest.

Author Contribution

APK: Carried out the primary survey and collected data in the region; LRD, BS and PMV, Managed the analyses of the study.

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